

VALUE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STEAM EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kun uchun juda ahamiyatli bo'lgan va ertaning asosiy mezini hisoblangan ta'lim tizimi, uning ahamiyati va STEAM ta'limining tutgan o'rni uning foydalari, o'quvchilarga ta'siri haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: STEAM, ta'lim, innovatsiya, integratsiya, kelajak, dunyoqarash, o'quv jarayoni, texnologiya va boshqalar.

Abstract: This article talks about the educational system, which is very important for today and is considered the main brain of tomorrow, its importance and the role of STEAM education, its benefits, and its impact on students.

Keywords: STEAM, education, innovation, integration, future, outlook, educational process, technology, etc.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассказывается о системе образования, которая очень важна на сегодняшний день и считается главным мозгом завтрашнего дня, ее важности и роли STEAM-образования, его пользе и влиянии на учащихся.

Ключевые слова: STEAM, образование, инновации, интеграция, будущее, перспективы, образовательный процесс, технологии и др.

The STEAM education system is a part of the education system that is developing day by day and is the only force that can cover the face of the world. provides In STEAM education, attention is paid to the main idea of the goal set forward. They are looked at and thought about from all sides, social and political, the benefits and harms of inventions, experiments, and all the disasters that they may cause in the future. is approached. The main idea of STEAM education is to conduct education in an integrated way, to teach the ability to discuss and think critically, taking into account the connection of all areas of education, science and technology, development, and business.

- Thinking about taking risks
- Becoming a resilient, problem solver
- Engaging in meaningful educational activities
- Value cooperation
- Honoring and collaborating with the creative process

The role of the STEAM education system in the education of primary school students is also incomparable. In this education, the task of STEAM education is to develop students' interest in nature and technology. To love what he does and motivate him to do it wholeheartedly.

This new approach to education is the logical result of combining theory and practice. STEAM was developed in America. Some schools took into account the careers of graduates and decided to combine subjects such as science, technology, engineering and mathematics, and this is how the STEM system was formed.

(Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics). Later, Art was added here, and now STEAM was finally formed. Teachers believe that knowledge of these subjects, or more precisely, these subjects, will help students become highly qualified specialists in the future. After all, children want to get good knowledge and apply it immediately. So, this idea has shown good results, isn't it?

The STEAM technology, in a different approach to education, ensures that knowledge is carried out in a mutually proportional way, rather than separately, and creates a criterion for this. The student feels that he has acquired non-standard thinking, different approach to the problem, creativity skills. Because STEAM includes the following subjects:

- S-science (natural science)
- T-technology (technology)
- E-engineering (engineering work)
- A-art (art)
- M-mathematics (mathematics)

The following statements were made at the STEAM forward international conference held in Jerusalem in 2014:

- Engaging children in STEAM. This education should begin at preschool age, so programs should be included in kindergartens
- The language of science is English. If you want to study science and become a scientist, you need to know this language.

- Steam educational programs for girls are needed. Girls in science can do things that boys can't because of their discipline.

- Science is fun! Science should be fun, it should be interesting and attractive for students.

In today's 21st century, there is no way to be behind, not to think, and to be limited. After all, today is the young generation of tomorrow. It is the introduction of this educational system to Uzbekistan, the goal of which is very big. Basically, as our head of state said, we should direct young people to free thinking and independent life. In this regard, STEAM technology comes in handy.

Great attention is paid to the combination of theoretical and practical knowledge. In the environment of STEAM education, children acquire knowledge, and they think that what they have learned should be applied in any situation.

STEAM educational system training is very interesting and not boring. Children who are busy with activities will not get bored during the lesson and will not wait for time. Because he works in an active team and in an environment he loves. The most important thing is that the activities or trainings that the children have done with their peers and the teacher will be more firmly established in the child's memory. time is also important.

In conclusion, we would like to emphasize that, compared to traditional teaching methods, the STEAM approach in high school allows children to conduct experiments, build models, independently create music and films, and turn their ideas into reality. and drives the creation of the final product. This educational

approach allows children to effectively combine theory and practical skills and facilitates university entrance and further studies.

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